

CONTRIBUTION TO STANDARDISATION

RESCALE WHITE PAPER 2025

<https://rescale-project.eu/>

Executive Summary

The EU-funded project RESCALE aims at enhancing the security and trust of software and hardware supply chains through a holistic cybersecurity assessment framework. By integrating advanced security assessment techniques, continuous monitoring processes, and blockchain-based trust mechanisms, RESCALE provides a novel approach to disclose cyber risks to potential users.

This white paper presents the objectives and approach of RESCALE with the intention to serve as a basis for interaction with key standardisation bodies, including ETSI TC CYBER, IETF SCITT, and CEN-CENELEC JTC 13. It also complements the project's Initial Exploitation Plan [1], where RESCALE's planned contributions to these specific bodies are detailed and quantified. It highlights RESCALE's results and innovations that can be translated into standards, supporting implementation of CRA Annex I and NIS2 Article 21 requirements, or otherwise leveraged to strengthen ongoing standardisation activities and discussions in supply chain security, certification, and trust management. The paper further outlines the standards relevant to RESCALE, demonstrating how the project takes them as input to its work while extending their scope through innovative concepts such as the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM). By doing so, RESCALE contributes to the evolution of standardised practices that can ensure trusted, transparent, and resilient supply chains in Europe and beyond. These practices are substantiated in RESCALE's High Level Architecture [2] and detailed in the project's Initial Exploitation Plan [1], where RESCALE's engagement with ETSI TC CYBER and IETF SCITT is outlined.

About RESCALE

Modern, interconnected supply chains—central to the EU’s digital economy—have become major cybersecurity risk vectors. In the last two years, the growing threat to software supply chains has become undeniable, with numerous high-profile attacks targeting this vulnerable area.

Notable incidents highlight a critical reality: software supply chains represent one of the largest unaddressed attack surfaces in cybersecurity today, whether organisations are building or deploying software. Current practices lack a standardised, transparent, and trusted way to continuously assess, certify, and ensure the security of both software and hardware elements within these supply chains. This gap aligns with priorities in the CRA and NIS2 for continuous security assessment and conformity evidence.

To address this challenge, RESCALE has been awarded funding of almost 5M Euros by the EU Commission Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement 101120962. The RESCALE platform enhances supply chain security by ensuring the protection of both hardware and software components, fostering trust and integrity across the entire supply chain.

Objectives

Design and develop a modular toolbox for auditing and enhancing supply chain security for hardware and software modules.

Detect and safeguard against vulnerabilities in hardware elements and enhance software security capabilities.

Provide a Trusted BOM approach to infuse trust in software and hardware supply chains and promote trusted updates.

About RESCALE

RESCALE introduces the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), which tracks and verifies components through a combination of static and dynamic security testing.

These tests generate trusted reports that are linked to a public blockchain. While the TBOMs themselves are not stored directly on the blockchain, cryptographic hashes of the reports are recorded to guarantee integrity and prevent tampering. This approach ensures transparency, traceability, and immutability without exposing sensitive data. By integrating blockchain technology and adhering to industry standards (e.g., NIST, ETSI, ISO/IEC 20243, CycloneDX), the platform provides comprehensive security assessments, enabling trusted updates and the secure integration of third-party components.

The vision of RESCALE is to establish secure-by-design and trusted supply chains that strengthen resilience against cyberattacks and foster confidence among vendors, auditors, regulators, and end-users.

Objectives

Demonstrate and validate the effectiveness and accuracy of proposed solutions in two industrial use cases led by Chocolate Cloud (Cloud Security) and Stritzinger GmbH (Hardware Security), targeting TRL4 maturity.

Promote uptake of secure supply chain standards and practices across EU industry sectors.

RESCALE Key Exploitable Results

RESCALE Platform

The RESCALE Platform strengthens supply chain security by assessing and certifying both hardware and software components. It introduces the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), which uses static and dynamic testing to generate trusted security reports. These reports are anchored on a blockchain through cryptographic hashes, ensuring transparency, traceability, and immutability while safeguarding sensitive data.

Dynamic Testing Module

The Dynamic Testing Module analyses running applications, binaries and hardware components – including side-channel leakage in hardware – to identify vulnerabilities and errors during execution. It produces the Dynamic Supply Chain Guarantee (DSCG), which captures findings from dynamic analysis, fuzzing, runtime monitoring, and hardware leakage assessment. The DSCG also supports CRA continuous-monitoring obligations and can complement emerging vulnerability disclosure standards.

Static Code Analysis Module

The Static Code Analysis Module examines source code without executing it to detect errors, vulnerabilities, and coding issues early in the development process. It generates the Static Supply Chain Guarantee (SSCG), offering developers structured insights into code quality and security, with its outputs designed to align with the assurance principles of Common Criteria (ISO/IEC 15408).

Advanced Visualisation Toolkit

The RESCALE Dashboard provides security operators with an interactive interface to monitor supply chain security states in real time. It integrates data from the testing modules and certification processes, offering role-based, customizable views that support decision-making and incident management. By enabling transparency and auditability, the dashboard aligns with the needs of emerging certification frameworks.

RESCALE Key Exploitable Results

Trust Storage Platform

The Trust Storage Platform is a secure repository for storing and managing trust-related information. By leveraging blockchain, it ensures that certification data and security evidence are stored transparently and cannot be tampered with.

TBOM Structure

The Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) defines a structured way to document and verify supply chain components. It extends existing BOM formats to include results from RESCALE's testing modules, creating a reproducible and traceable certification artifact for both hardware and software.

RAISE

RAISE (REST API Intelligent Security Explorer) is an intelligent REST API fuzzing tool that extends Microsoft's RESTler with machine learning techniques. It automatically generates sequences of API requests to uncover hidden security flaws in cloud and microservice-based architectures. Its outputs align with NIST SP 800-115 on API testing and can inform future ETSI work on API assurance.

Main outcomes of RESCALE suitable for standardisation include:

- 1. RESCALE Reference Architecture and Glossary:** By consolidating terminology and defining architectural elements for trusted supply chains, RESCALE provides a system design blueprint and glossary (ex. TBOM: Trusted Bill of Materials, SSCG: Static Supply Chain Guarantee, DSCG: Dynamic Supply Chain Guarantee, BoV: Bill of Vulnerabilities). A common vocabulary mitigates fragmentation in supply chain terminology across CRA, NIS2, and ISO/IEC standards. The architecture and glossary are further detailed in the High-Level Architecture deliverable and can serve as valuable reference inputs to European and international standardisation bodies working on supply chain security and assurance.
- 2. Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM):** RESCALE introduces the TBOM, a structured and traceable way to certify hardware and software components. By extending existing BOM formats with security test results (SSCG, DSCG, BoV, proof of testing), the TBOM can serve as the foundation for a European standard for supply chain certification artefacts.
- 3. Blockchain-based Trust Storage:** The RESCALE Trust Storage platform ensures that certification evidence is immutable, transparent, and tamper-proof through cryptographic anchoring on blockchain. This approach could be standardised as a trusted evidence repository model for supply chain certification. This outcome can define a “Trusted Certification Evidence Repository” profile that maps the Trust Storage Platform to existing standards and controls already referenced by RESCALE—evidence identifiers and linkage via CycloneDX/ECMA-424 and TBOM, registration and verification flows via IETF SCITT signed statements, governance and ISMS controls via ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 20243, and evidence signing and key protection with X.509, PKCS7/CMS, and PKCS11—ensuring an interoperable, certifiable evidence lifecycle aligned with NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act. Recommended engagement points are IETF SCITT WG (interoperable evidence registration/verification), ETSI TC CYBER (conformance and policy alignment with EU frameworks), CEN-CENELEC JTC 13 (EU conformity models), ISO/IEC and IEC communities for integration into global assurance frameworks, and coordination with ENISA to align with EU cybersecurity certification schemes, leveraging ongoing RESCALE liaison activities with SCITT to seed profiles and interop demonstrations.

RESCALE and the European Standards

Conformity with existing standards

Standards play a fundamental role in strengthening cybersecurity and supply chain trust across Europe and globally. The complexity of modern hardware and software supply chains requires harmonised approaches to security evaluation, traceability, and certification. The RESCALE project has identified a set of standards, standardisation bodies and EU directives that directly align with its objectives and that should be carefully monitored and influenced during the project's lifecycle. RESCALE also provides innovations that can be mapped against and enhance these frameworks, contributing to their evolution. These bodies and announced strategies include:

International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)

The ISO is the leading global body for developing and publishing international standards across industries, ensuring product, service, and system quality, safety, and efficiency. RESCALE aligns with ISO/IEC 27001:2022 Annex A controls addressing supplier and supply-chain security (A.5.19–A.5.23), configuration management (A.8.9), and monitoring (A.8.16). These controls provide the framework within which TBOM generation and continuous validation contribute to certification evidence. The project takes these standards as key inputs, using them to guide the design of the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) and continuous validation mechanisms, thereby ensuring that RESCALE outcomes are aligned with established international best practices.

European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)

ENISA is the EU's centre of expertise in cybersecurity, supporting Member States in building capabilities, fostering cooperation among CSIRTs, and developing certification frameworks under the EU Cybersecurity Act. RESCALE aligns its TBOM assurance model with ENISA's forthcoming EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (EUCS) and related schemes, ensuring its results are compatible with the EU-wide conformity assessment framework.

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)

ETSI is a leading European standardisation body that develops globally applicable standards for a wide range of ICT domains. Through its dedicated Technical Committee on Cybersecurity (TC CYBER), ETSI plays a central role in defining horizontal cybersecurity standards that support EU regulations and policies, including NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA). Its work on supply chain risk management, security assurance of ICT products, and trusted software updates is directly relevant to RESCALE. The project takes ETSI EN 303 645 (IoT security) and ETSI TR 103 838 (Supply-Chain Risk Management) as important inputs to ensure that the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), continuous validation mechanisms, and certification processes are consistent with European best practices and evolving regulatory frameworks.

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)

The IETF develops open standards that shape the Internet, with the Supply Chain Integrity, Transparency, and Trust (SCITT) working group being particularly relevant for RESCALE. SCITT aims to define interoperable mechanisms for trustworthy supply chain operations. RESCALE contributes by providing TBOM-based traceability and immutable blockchain-backed trust anchors, which could be another use case for the IETF SCITT work for providing specific examples of supply chain security statements.

International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)

The IEC produces global standards for electrical, electronic, and related technologies, supporting safety, quality, and interoperability. Its work underpins conformity assessment and risk management frameworks across industries. RESCALE proposes security evaluation methodologies for hardware components, supporting IEC's mission to ensure safe, resilient, and sustainable technologies across interconnected supply chains.

CEN and CENELEC

CEN and CENELEC are Europe's primary standardisation bodies, covering diverse domains including ICT, cybersecurity, electrical engineering, and digital technologies. They play a central role in aligning European standards with EU legislation and Horizon Europe priorities. RESCALE's outcomes – particularly the TBOM and continuous security testing frameworks – can provide valuable input to ongoing CEN-CENELEC efforts on cybersecurity and digital trust, helping ensure a coherent European approach to secure supply chains.

The NIS2 Directive

The revised EU Directive on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2) expands the scope of the original NIS Directive, introducing stricter requirements for risk management, supply chain security, and incident reporting. It applies to a broader range of sectors, including digital infrastructure, manufacturing, energy, healthcare, financial markets, and public administration. Given RESCALE's focus on software and hardware supply chain security, the project directly supports NIS2 objectives by introducing the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), continuous security validation mechanisms, and

immutable blockchain-backed certification. These elements provide concrete tools for organisations to comply with NIS2 requirements on supply chain risk management and transparent security assurance. Furthermore, RESCALE outcomes – such as security certification reports (SSCG, DSCG) and TBOM structures – can be leveraged as best practices and evidence to facilitate cross-border information sharing and conformity assessment, thus reinforcing the culture of trust and security envisioned by NIS2 across all EU Member States.

The Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)

The EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) establishes mandatory cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements, including both hardware and software, throughout their entire lifecycle. It focuses on secure design, vulnerability management, and timely incident reporting, aiming to ensure that digital products placed on the EU market meet high cybersecurity standards. Given RESCALE's focus on software and hardware supply chain security, the project directly supports CRA objectives by providing the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), continuous security validation mechanisms, and immutable blockchain-backed certification. These capabilities enable manufacturers, distributors, and users to demonstrate compliance with CRA requirements, ensuring secure development and transparent product assurance. RESCALE outputs – such as TBOM structure – can serve as practical tools and best practices to facilitate CRA compliance, thereby reinforcing the overall resilience of digital products across the EU. Specific obligations which are part of the CRA, such as vulnerability reporting requirements, are greatly assisted by the concept of a cryptographically verifiable Trusted BOM acting as the single source of information for a component, product or tool. This, coupled with continuous vulnerability detection, equips organisations to better enable compliance with the CRA.

Standards of interest

RESCALE has identified the following standards as highly relevant for its work and are clustered into the following thematic areas:

1. Supply Chain Security Management

- ISO/IEC 28000 series (Supply Chain Security Management): Establishes requirements for security assurance in logistics and supply chain operations, safeguarding against risks such as theft, counterfeiting, and terrorism.
- ISO/IEC 20243 (Open Trusted Technology Provider Standard): Provides guidelines for mitigating ICT supply chain risks, ensuring trusted development and distribution of hardware and software.
- ISO/IEC 27000 series (Information Security Management Systems): Defines requirements and controls for secure information handling across organisations, supporting risk management in supply chains.
- ISO/IEC 27001:2022 includes Annex A controls, such as supplier management, cryptographic protections, and monitoring.
- NIST SP 800-161 (Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management, C-SCRM): Offers a structured approach to integrating supply chain risk into enterprise-wide risk management practices.

2. Security Testing and Assurance

- ISO/IEC 15408 & ISO/IEC 18045 (Common Criteria): Provide a globally recognised framework for structured security evaluations, which RESCALE extends with TBOM-driven continuous assurance.
- NIST SP 800-115 (Technical Guide to Information Security Testing and Assessment): Offers practical guidance on security testing, including vulnerability scanning and penetration testing, reflected in RESCALE's static and dynamic testing modules.
- CEN/CENELEC EN 17640 (Cybersecurity Evaluation for ICT Products): Establishes methods for auditing ICT product security, which can complement RESCALE's hardware/software component assurance.

3. Transparency, Integrity, and Trust Models

- CycloneDX (ECMA-424): International SBOM standard that RESCALE extends into the TBOM concept, embedding test results and blockchain-backed traceability.
- SPDX (ISO/IEC 5962:2021): Open SBOM standard for representing SBOM information, provenance, licenses, security, and more.
- IETF Supply Chain Integrity, Transparency, and Trust (SCITT): Provides mechanisms for immutable registration of supply chain artefacts through signed statements, aligned with RESCALE's blockchain-based verification.
- ISO/TC 307 (Blockchain and DLT): The principal ISO committee for blockchain/DLT standardisation, providing a neutral venue to align the Trust Storage repository model with broader DLT interoperability and governance practices.
- European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI): Adopts W3C VCs/VPs for EU trust frameworks, offering a natural European pathway for interoperable evidence portability and conformity with eID ecosystems.
- Digital Signature Standards:
 - X.509: Manages identity certificates for authentication and trust.
 - PKCS#7/CMS: Enables cryptographic signing of artefacts.
 - PKCS#11: Protects private key storage in secure hardware tokens.

4. Vulnerability and Incident Management

- ISO/IEC 29147: Provides best practices for responsible vulnerability disclosure, supporting RESCALE's commitment to transparent and effective security management.
- NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF): Guides organisations in managing cybersecurity risks, covering identity, protection, detection, response, and recovery – all relevant to RESCALE's security visualisation and incident response components.
- ETSI standards (e.g., ETSI TVRA, ETSI EN 303 645): Provide methodologies for threat/vulnerability risk assessment and IoT security requirements, complementing RESCALE's component-level assurance.

5. Data Protection and EU Regulatory Landscape

- CEN-CENELEC JTC 13 standards: Cover EU-wide cybersecurity and data protection frameworks, relevant for aligning TBOM with conformity assessment models.
- EU NIS2 Directive: Strengthens cybersecurity requirements for essential and important entities across critical sectors, aligning with RESCALE's goals for supply chain resilience.
- EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA): Establishes mandatory cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements. RESCALE contributes by offering automated security testing and continuous assurance mechanisms that align with CRA obligations.

Mapping RESCALE Outcomes to Relevant Standards and Frameworks

RESCALE Outcome / KER	Relevant Standards / Directives / Frameworks	Rationale / Mapping
RESCALE Platform	ISO/IEC 28000, ISO/IEC 27000, ISO/IEC 20243, NIS2, CRA, CEN-CENELEC JTC 13	Supports secure supply chain operations, continuous risk management, and regulatory compliance. TBOM enables traceability, transparency, and accountability, aligning with CRA and NIS2 requirements.
Static Code Analysis Module	ISO/IEC 15408 & 18045, NIST SP 800-115, ETSI TVRA	Provides a structured evaluation of source code for vulnerabilities, consistent with Common Criteria security testing methodologies and ETSI/TVRA risk assessment approaches.
Dynamic Testing Module	ISO/IEC 15408 & 18045, NIST SP 800-115, ETSI EN 303 645, NIST CSF	Validates running binaries and applications to detect vulnerabilities and security issues, supporting standards for operational security assessment and incident detection.

Mapping RESCALE Outcomes to Relevant Standards and Frameworks

Advanced Visualisation Toolkit (Dashboard)	NIST CSF, ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27000 series	Provides real-time monitoring, incident detection, and reporting to support security management processes and compliance with information security standards.
Trust Storage Platform	ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 20243, CycloneDX, IETF SCITT, Digital Signature Standards (X.509, PKCS#7, PKCS#11)	Ensures secure storage and verification of trust-related data. Blockchain and cryptographic standards provide integrity and immutability for TBOMs.
TBOM Structure	CycloneDX (ECMA-424), ISO/IEC 20243, SPDX (ISO/IEC 5962:2021) NIS2, CRA	Standardises the Trusted Bill of Materials for secure component tracking. Supports compliance with supply chain regulations and CRA cybersecurity requirements.
RAISE (REST API Intelligent Security Explorer)	NIST SP 800-115, NIST CSF, ETSI EN 303 645	Automates API security testing using ML-enhanced fuzzing, ensuring web services meet security assessment and operational standards.

Potential for Collaboration

RESCALE seeks to establish strong ties with standardisation bodies to ensure alignment with best-in-class industry practices and maximize the impact and applicability of its results. By engaging proactively with relevant standardisation initiatives, the project aims to support the development and adoption of secure supply chain practices across the EU.

As part of these efforts, Athena Research Centre presented the RESCALE project at the SCITT working group during IETF 123 in Madrid. The presentation introduced RESCALE concepts and initiated discussions on how the project can leverage the SCITT standard, as well as explore avenues for collaboration. Slides are available upon request. Through such interactions, RESCALE partners aim to contribute to the evolution of next-generation standards for software and hardware supply chain security, ensuring that the project outcomes are both practical and aligned with international standards.

References

- [1] RESCALE Consortium, "D6.4 – Initial Exploitation Plan," Project Deliverable, Horizon Europe, 2025.
- [2] RESCALE Consortium, "D2.6 – High Level Architecture (final version)," Project Deliverable, Horizon Europe, 2025.

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